

Examining the Differential Effects of Brand Free-Riding Dimensions on Brand Loyalty in Southern Ethiopia

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Abstract: This study examines the differential impact of brand free-riding dimensions on brand loyalty among consumers of soap and detergent brands in selected cities of Southern Ethiopia. Brand free-riding is conceptualized from a consumer-perception perspective and operationalized through packaging similarity, visual appearance similarity, brand name and labeling similarity, and overall brand identity resemblance. A quantitative, cross-sectional design was employed based on survey data collected from 450 consumers. Correlation and multiple regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationships among variables. The results indicate that all dimensions of brand free-riding are positively and significantly associated with brand loyalty ($r = 0.708$ to 0.761 , $p < 0.01$). However, only brand identity resemblance shows a statistically significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.629$, $p < 0.001$), while packaging similarity ($\beta = 0.184$, $p = 0.095$), visual appearance similarity ($\beta = 0.178$, $p = 0.078$), and brand name and labeling similarity ($\beta = -0.215$, $p = 0.064$) do not exhibit significant independent effects. The model explains a substantial proportion of variance in brand loyalty ($R^2 = 0.588$). The findings suggest that consumers rely primarily on holistic brand identity cues rather than isolated brand elements when forming loyalty judgments, reflecting the integrated nature of perceived brand similarity. The study contributes to branding literature by providing a multidimensional perspective on brand free-riding and highlights the importance of maintaining a distinct overall brand identity in competitive FMCG markets.

Keywords: Brand Free-Riding; Brand Loyalty; Packaging Similarity; Visual Appearance Similarity; Brand Identity Resemblance; FMCG; Developing Markets

1. Introduction

Brand loyalty is critical in fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) markets, where frequent purchases and low switching costs intensify competition among brands (Keller, 2013). In such contexts, consumers rely heavily on observable cues such as packaging, visual appearance, and brand names to guide rapid purchase decisions (Hoyer & Brown, 1990). The effectiveness of branding therefore depends on the clarity and distinctiveness of these cues as signals of product identity and quality (Tülin Erdem, 1998).

However, imitation-based practices increasingly challenge brand distinctiveness. Brand free-riding, characterized by the replication of visible brand cues to benefit from established brand recognition, can reduce differentiation and distort consumer perception (M. Saunders et al., 2009); (Mitchell & Papavassiliou, 1999). When competing brands appear similar, consumers may experience difficulty distinguishing between alternatives, which can weaken brand signals and reduce loyalty (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001).

Although prior research has examined brand imitation, it has largely treated brand free-riding as a unified construct. Limited attention has been given to whether different dimensions of similarity exert varying effects on brand loyalty (Horen & Pieters, 2012). This gap is particularly relevant in developing markets such as Ethiopia, where consumers frequently encounter visually similar products in competitive retail environments.

Accordingly, this study examines the differential impact of brand free-riding dimensions on brand loyalty among soap and detergent consumers in selected cities of Southern Ethiopia.

1.1 Problem Statement

Brand loyalty remains critical in fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) markets, where frequent purchases and low switching costs intensify competition (Keller, 2013). However, imitation-based practices that replicate visible brand cues can distort brand signals and reduce consumers' ability to distinguish between competing products, particularly in low-involvement purchase contexts (M. Saunders et al., 2009); (Mitchell & Papavassiliou, 1999).

Existing research has largely treated brand free-riding as a unified construct, with limited attention to how its different dimensions influence brand loyalty. Given that consumers process brand cues differently, specific forms of similarity may exert varying effects on loyalty outcomes (Horen & Pieters, 2012). This limitation is particularly relevant in developing markets such as Ethiopia, where consumers frequently encounter visually similar products in competitive retail environments.

Accordingly, there is a need to examine brand free-riding as a multidimensional phenomenon and to assess the differential impact of its dimensions on brand loyalty.

1.2. Literature Review

1.2.1. Concept of Brand Free-Riding

Brand free-riding refers to the imitation of salient brand cues, including packaging, visual appearance, and naming structures, to benefit from the recognition and goodwill of established brands without equivalent investment in brand development (M. Saunders et al., 2009). Unlike counterfeiting, it operates primarily through perceptual similarity that shapes consumer judgment without necessarily violating legal boundaries (Phau et al., 2009).

From a consumer perspective, the significance of brand free-riding lies in its effect on how brand signals are interpreted during purchase decisions. In low-involvement contexts, consumers rely on observable cues as heuristic indicators of quality and reliability (Tülin Erdem, 1998). When competing brands display similar visual or symbolic elements, perceived differentiation declines, increasing the likelihood of misattribution and association transfer (Mitchell & Papavassiliou, 1999). Empirical evidence further suggests that such similarity can activate associations linked to established brands, enabling imitative products to benefit from transferred perceptions (Horen & Pieters, 2012). Thus, brand free-riding is best understood as a perception-driven phenomenon with direct implications for consumer evaluation and choice.

1.2.2. Dimensions of Brand Free-Riding

Brand free-riding operates through multiple forms of perceived similarity, each influencing consumer evaluation differently. Distinguishing these dimensions allows a more precise assessment of how imitation affects brand-related outcomes.

Packaging similarity arises when competing products adopt similar structural and design elements, reducing brand distinctiveness and increasing the likelihood of misidentification in low-involvement contexts (Hoyer & Brown, 1990); (Mitchell & Papavassiliou, 1999).

Visual similarity, reflected in color schemes and graphical presentation, plays a particularly strong role in brand recognition due to rapid visual processing. Similar visual cues increase perceptual overlap and confusion, especially in routine purchase situations (Horen & Pieters, 2012).

Brand name and labeling similarity affects the clarity of brand identification by creating phonetic or structural resemblance between competing brands. Such similarity can lead to misattribution and associative transfer, particularly under time constraints (Aaker, 1991); (Horen & Pieters, 2012).

Brand identity resemblance captures the overall similarity across multiple brand cues. Because consumers process brand elements holistically, convergence of these cues can make brands appear interchangeable, thereby weakening perceived uniqueness (Kapferer, 2012); (Loken et al., 2008).

1.2.3. Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty reflects a consumer's sustained preference and commitment toward a brand, expressed through both attitudinal attachment and consistent purchasing behavior (Oliver, 1999). In FMCG markets, where switching costs are low and alternatives are abundant, loyalty plays a critical role in maintaining stable demand (Ehrenberg et al., 2004).

However, loyalty is sensitive to the clarity of brand differentiation. When competing brands are perceived as similar, the value of maintaining brand preference may decline, increasing switching tendencies (Tülin Erdem, 1998). This indicates that factors reducing brand distinctiveness, such as imitation-based similarity, can directly influence loyalty outcomes.

Analytically, brand loyalty is commonly reflected through repurchase intention, preference stability, and resistance to switching, capturing both behavioral consistency and commitment in competitive settings (Dick & Basu, 1994).

1.2.4. Theoretical Foundations

The relationship between brand free-riding and brand loyalty is grounded in brand signaling theory and consumer confusion theory, which explain how consumers interpret and respond to brand-related cues.

Brand signaling theory posits that brands serve as signals of product quality under conditions of information asymmetry (Tülin Erdem, 1998). The effectiveness of these signals depends on their clarity and credibility. Imitation-based similarity can weaken signal distinctiveness, reducing informational value and undermining consumer trust, thereby affecting loyalty.

Consumer confusion theory explains how similarity among competing brands disrupts consumer decision-making (Mitchell & Papavassiliou, 1999). In low-involvement contexts, high resemblance increases the likelihood of misidentification and reduces decision confidence (Hoyer & Brown, 1990). Such confusion can lead to switching behavior, providing a behavioral explanation for how brand free-riding weakens brand loyalty.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

Brand free-riding influences consumer evaluation by reducing perceived differentiation and affecting brand-related judgments (Mitchell & Papavassiliou, 1999). However, the effects of similarity may vary depending on the type of brand cue.

Packaging similarity can affect product recognition and increase the likelihood of misidentification in low-involvement contexts (Hoyer & Brown, 1990). Visual appearance similarity, particularly in color and graphical elements, influences brand recognition through rapid visual processing (Horen & Pieters, 2012). Brand name and labeling similarity may create phonetic and structural resemblance, leading to confusion in brand identification (Aaker, 1991). In contrast, brand identity resemblance reflects the overall similarity across multiple cues and is expected to exert a stronger influence, as consumers process brand information holistically (Kapferer, 2012).

Based on these arguments, the following hypotheses are proposed:

1. H1: Packaging similarity has a significant effect on brand loyalty.
2. H2: Visual appearance similarity has a significant effect on brand loyalty.
3. H3: Brand name and labeling similarity has a significant effect on brand loyalty.
4. H4: Brand identity resemblance has a significant effect on brand loyalty.

1.4 Objectives and Significance

This study aims to address the identified research gap by examining how different dimensions of brand free-riding influence brand loyalty in the soap and detergent market. By adopting a quantitative approach, the study evaluates the extent to which perceived similarities across brand-related cues affect consumer loyalty in selected cities of Southern Ethiopia. Specifically, the study will:

1. Assess the effect of packaging similarity on brand loyalty.
2. Examine the influence of visual appearance similarity on brand loyalty.
3. Determine the impact of brand name and labeling similarity on brand loyalty.
4. Evaluate the effect of overall brand identity resemblance on brand loyalty.

The significance of this study lies in advancing the understanding of brand free-riding as a multidimensional phenomenon and its differential effects on consumer loyalty. The findings provide practical insights for brand managers and marketers in designing more distinctive brand strategies, while also offering context-specific evidence relevant to competitive FMCG markets in developing economies.

1.5 Research Questions

1. What is the effect of packaging similarity on brand loyalty?
2. How does visual appearance similarity influence brand loyalty?
3. What is the impact of brand name and labeling similarity on brand loyalty?
4. How does brand identity resemblance affect brand loyalty?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to examine the impact of brand free-riding on brand loyalty among consumers of soap and detergent products in selected cities of Southern Ethiopia. A quantitative approach is appropriate for systematically measuring consumer perceptions and testing relationships among variables using statistical techniques (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

The cross-sectional design enables the collection of data at a single point in time, allowing the study to identify patterns and associations between brand free-riding dimensions and brand loyalty within a competitive market context (M. Saunders et al., 2009). This approach is particularly suitable for FMCG markets, where consumer decisions are frequent and influenced by immediate perceptions of brand-related cues.

Given the low-involvement nature of soap and detergent purchases, consumers often rely on observable cues such as packaging and visual appearance during decision-making (Hoyer & Brown, 1990). The use of a structured survey instrument therefore provides a reliable means of capturing these perceptions and evaluating their influence on loyalty outcomes. Overall, the chosen design ensures objectivity, analytical rigor, and suitability for examining the differential effects of brand free-riding dimensions on brand loyalty.

2.2. Participants and Sampling

The target population for this study consists of consumers of soap and detergent products in selected cities of Southern Ethiopia, namely: Hawassa, Shashemene, and Dilla. These urban centers represent active retail markets with diverse consumer segments and high exposure to competing brands. A purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure that respondents had prior experience with purchasing and evaluating soap and detergent brands, thereby enabling meaningful assessment of brand-related perceptions.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered through Google Forms. The survey was designed with a forced-response format, requiring respondents to complete each question before proceeding to the next. This design ensured complete responses and eliminated item-level nonresponse, resulting in a zero non-response rate in the collected dataset.

The final dataset comprises $N = 450$ valid responses. The sample reflects a diverse distribution of consumers across demographic characteristics such as age, gender, and purchasing experience. This diversity enhances the representativeness of consumer perceptions within the selected urban markets. The use of non-probability purposive sampling is consistent with prior consumer behavior research where respondents are selected based on their relevance to the research context (M. N. K. Saunders et al., 2019).

2.3 Measurement Instrument

The survey instrument was developed based on established constructs in branding and consumer behavior literature, with items adapted to reflect the context of soap and detergent markets. The questionnaire was designed to capture consumers' perceptions of brand free-riding and brand loyalty using structured measurement scales (Keller, 2013); (Yoo & Donthu, 2001).

The instrument included multiple-item measures covering the following dimensions:

1. Packaging Similarity: Measured through items assessing perceived similarity in packaging structure, layout, and design among competing brands.
2. Visual Appearance Similarity: Assessed using items related to color schemes, graphics, and overall visual presentation of brands.
3. Brand Name and Labeling Similarity: Measured through items capturing perceived resemblance in brand names and labeling formats.
4. Brand Identity Resemblance: Evaluated through items reflecting overall similarity in brand identity across multiple brand cues.
5. Brand Loyalty: Measured using indicators of repurchase intention, preference stability, and resistance to switching, reflecting both behavioral and attitudinal loyalty (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001).
6. Demographic Variables: Included age, gender, and purchasing experience to describe the sample characteristics.

All items were measured using a Likert-type scale to capture the degree of agreement with each statement. The use of structured survey instruments allows for reliable quantification of consumer perceptions and supports statistical analysis of relationships among variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

2.4 Reliability Analysis

The internal consistency of the measurement scales was assessed using Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951). As presented in Table 1, all constructs exhibit strong internal consistency, with alpha values ranging from 0.853 to 0.905. These values exceed the recommended threshold of 0.70, indicating satisfactory reliability (Hair et al., 2019). The results confirm that the measurement items reliably capture the underlying constructs and are suitable for subsequent statistical analysis.

Table 1: Reliability Analysis of Study Constructs

Construct	Dimension	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Brand Free-Riding	Packaging Similarity	4	0.898
	Color and Visual Appearance Similarity	4	0.853
	Brand Name and Labeling Similarity	4	0.876
	Brand Identity Resemblance	4	0.876
Brand Loyalty	Repurchase Intention	4	0.898
	Brand Preference Stability	4	0.903
	Resistance to Switching	4	0.905

Source: Survey data (2025); author's computation.

2.5 Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected through a structured survey administered to consumers in selected cities of Southern Ethiopia. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, assured of confidentiality, and participation was voluntary, with only those providing informed consent included in the survey. The questionnaire was prepared in both English and Amharic to ensure clarity and accessibility and was administered via Google Forms using a forced-response format, which required respondents to complete each item before proceeding, thereby ensuring complete data and resulting in zero item-level nonresponse. The data collection process adhered to established ethical guidelines for survey-based research (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

2.6 Data Preparation and Cleaning

The collected data were carefully reviewed before analysis to identify any inconsistencies, response biases, or potential errors. Since the survey was administered using a forced-response format, the dataset contained no missing values. Each response was examined to ensure validity, and any inconsistent entries were excluded to maintain data quality. The final dataset was then coded and prepared for statistical analysis using SPSS. The data screening process followed established quantitative research guidelines to ensure reliability and accuracy (Hair et al., 2019).

2.7 Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS and proceeded in two main stages:

2.7.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and frequencies, were computed to summarize respondents' demographic characteristics and key study variables. These measures provide an overview of consumers' perceptions of brand free-riding dimensions and brand loyalty.

2.7.2 Inferential Statistics

To examine the relationships between brand free-riding dimensions and brand loyalty:

- Pearson's correlation analysis was used to assess the strength and direction of associations among variables.
- Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the impact of packaging similarity, visual similarity, brand name and labeling similarity, and brand identity resemblance on brand loyalty.
- Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values were examined to detect potential multicollinearity issues (Hair et al., 2019).

To assess differences across demographic groups:

- One-way ANOVA was applied to test for significant differences in brand loyalty across demographic categories.
- Post-hoc tests (Tukey HSD) were conducted for pairwise comparisons where significant differences were identified.

2.7.3 Model Specification

To examine the relationship between brand free-riding dimensions and brand loyalty, multiple linear regression analysis was employed. The following model was specified:

$$\text{Brand Loyalty} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(PS) + \beta_2(VAS) + \beta_3(BNLS) + \beta_4(BIR) + \varepsilon$$

Where:

- PS represents packaging similarity,
- VAS represents visual appearance similarity,
- BNLS represents brand name and labeling similarity,
- BIR represents brand identity resemblance, and
- ε is the error term.

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents the empirical findings of the study and discusses the results in relation to the research objectives and existing literature. The analysis begins with descriptive and correlation results, followed by regression analysis and interpretation.

3.1 Descriptive and Correlation Results

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the study variables. The mean scores for brand free-riding dimensions range from 2.34 to 2.51, indicating a moderate level of perceived similarity among competing soap and detergent brands. Visual appearance similarity ($M = 2.51$) and brand identity resemblance ($M = 2.50$) exhibit relatively higher perceived similarity, while packaging similarity ($M = 2.34$) shows the lowest mean.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Statistics								
		Packaging Similarity (Composite Score)	Color and Visual Appearance Similarity (Composite Score)	Brand Name and Labeling Similarity (Composite Score)	Brand Identity Resemblance (Composite Score)	Repurchase Intention (Composite Score)	Brand Preference Stability (Composite Score)	Resistance to Switching (Composite Score)
N	Valid	450	450	450	450	450	450	450
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.3411	2.5061	2.4450	2.5000	2.6411	2.6228	2.6106
Std. Deviation		.96603	.94317	1.00300	.94563	1.05134	1.03680	1.07442
Minimum		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum		4.75	4.50	4.75	4.75	5.00	5.00	5.00

Source: Survey data (2025); Author's computation

With respect to brand loyalty, the mean scores for repurchase intention ($M = 2.64$), brand preference stability ($M = 2.62$), and resistance to switching ($M = 2.61$) indicate a moderate level of consumer loyalty. The consistency across these dimensions suggests relatively stable loyalty-related responses.

The Pearson correlation results reported in Table 3 indicate that all dimensions of brand free-riding are positively and significantly associated with brand loyalty ($r = 0.708$ to 0.761 , $p < 0.01$). Among the dimensions, brand identity resemblance shows the strongest association ($r = 0.761$), followed by visual appearance similarity ($r = 0.735$), packaging similarity ($r = 0.712$), and brand name and labeling similarity ($r = 0.708$).

Table 3: Correlation Matrix of Brand Free-Riding Dimensions and Brand Loyalty

Correlations						
		Packaging Similarity (Composite Score)	Color and Visual Appearance Similarity (Composite Score)	Brand Name and Labeling Similarity (Composite Score)	Brand Identity Resemblance (Composite Score)	Brand Loyalty (Composite Score)
Packaging Similarity (Composite Score)	Pearson Correlation	1	.930**	.952**	.902**	.712**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	450	450	450	450	450
Color and Visual Appearance Similarity (Composite Score)	Pearson Correlation	.930**	1	.925**	.929**	.735**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	450	450	450	450	450
Brand Name and Labeling Similarity (Composite Score)	Pearson Correlation	.952**	.925**	1	.927**	.708**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	450	450	450	450	450
Brand Identity Resemblance (Composite Score)	Pearson Correlation	.902**	.929**	.927**	1	.761**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	450	450	450	450	450
Brand Loyalty (Composite Score)	Pearson Correlation	.712**	.735**	.708**	.761**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	450	450	450	450	450

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey data (2025); Author's computation

However, Table 3 also reveals very high correlations among the independent variables ($r = 0.902$ to 0.952), indicating substantial overlap among the dimensions. This suggests that consumers tend to perceive different forms of brand similarity as closely related, which has implications for regression analysis.

3.2 Regression Results

The regression results presented in Tables 4-6 show that the overall model is statistically significant ($F = 159.069$, $p < 0.001$) and explains a substantial proportion of variance in brand loyalty ($R^2 = 0.588$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.585$). This indicates that brand free-riding dimensions collectively provide strong explanatory power.

Table 4: Model Summary of the Effect of Brand Free-Riding on Brand Loyalty

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.767 ^a	.588	.585	.64575
a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Identity Resemblance (Composite Score), Packaging Similarity (Composite Score), Color and Visual Appearance Similarity (Composite Score), Brand Name and Labeling Similarity (Composite Score)				

Source: Survey data (2025); Author's computation

Table 5: ANOVA Results of the Regression Model

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	265.319	4	66.330	159.069	.000 ^b
	Residual	185.560	445	.417		
	Total	450.878	449			
a. Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty (Composite Score)						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Identity Resemblance (Composite Score), Packaging Similarity (Composite Score), Color and Visual Appearance Similarity (Composite Score), Brand Name and Labeling Similarity (Composite Score)						

Source: Survey data (2025); Author's computation

At the individual level, the coefficients reported in Table 6 reveal differential effects across dimensions. Brand identity resemblance has a strong and statistically significant positive effect on brand loyalty ($\beta = 0.629$, $p < 0.001$), indicating its dominant influence.

In contrast, packaging similarity ($\beta = 0.184$, $p = 0.095$) and visual appearance similarity ($\beta = 0.178$, $p = 0.078$) show positive but statistically insignificant effects, while brand name and labeling similarity exhibit a negative and marginally insignificant effect ($\beta = -0.215$, $p = 0.064$). These results indicate that individual dimensions do not contribute equally when considered simultaneously.

Table 6: Regression Coefficients for Brand Free-Riding Dimensions

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.563	.088		6.373	.000
	Packaging Similarity (Composite Score)	.191	.114	.184	1.673	.095
	Color and Visual Appearance Similarity (Composite Score)	.189	.107	.178	1.765	.078
	Brand Name and Labeling Similarity (Composite Score)	-.215	.116	-.215	-1.854	.064
	Brand Identity Resemblance (Composite Score)	.666	.099	.629	6.707	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty (Composite Score)

Source: Survey data (2025); Author's computation

Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty (Composite Score)

Multicollinearity diagnostics presented in Table 7 indicate elevated Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values ranging from 9.503 to 14.557, exceeding commonly accepted thresholds (Hair et al., 2019). This confirms the presence of substantial multicollinearity among the independent variables, reflecting a high degree of shared variance across the dimensions of brand free-riding. The findings suggest that these dimensions are not fully independent in consumers' perceptions but are closely intertwined. Consequently, the regression coefficients should be interpreted with caution, as multicollinearity may affect the stability and statistical significance of individual predictors, despite their strong bivariate associations with brand loyalty. This pattern further indicates that brand free-riding operates as a multidimensional yet integrated perceptual phenomenon.

Table 7: Multicollinearity Diagnostics of the Independent Variables

Independent Variables	Tolerance	VIF
Packaging Similarity (Composite Score)	0.076	13.095
Color and Visual Appearance Similarity (Composite Score)	0.091	11.029
Brand Name and Labeling Similarity (Composite Score)	0.069	14.557
Brand Identity Resemblance (Composite Score)	0.105	9.503

Source: Survey data (2025); Author's computation

3.3 Discussion of Findings

The findings demonstrate that while all dimensions of brand free-riding are positively associated with brand loyalty, only brand identity resemblance remains a statistically significant predictor when the effects are analyzed jointly. This indicates that consumers respond more strongly to the overall similarity of brand identity rather than to isolated elements such as packaging or naming.

This result suggests that consumers process brand cues holistically, particularly in low-involvement FMCG contexts where purchase decisions are made quickly and rely on overall impressions rather than detailed evaluation. The dominant effect of brand identity resemblance is consistent with prior research indicating that combined visual and symbolic similarity can activate existing brand associations and influence consumer responses (Horen & Pieters, 2012).

The non-significant effects of packaging similarity, visual appearance similarity, and brand name and labeling similarity observed in Table 6 should be interpreted with caution. The high intercorrelations among the independent variables reported in Table 3, together with elevated VIF values in Table 7, indicate the presence of substantial multicollinearity. This suggests that the dimensions of brand free-riding are closely intertwined in consumers' perceptions and may not operate as fully independent predictors. As a result, multicollinearity may have suppressed the individual statistical significance of some variables in the regression model, even though they exhibit strong bivariate relationships with brand loyalty.

These findings highlight that brand free-riding is better understood as a multidimensional and integrated phenomenon, where different forms of similarity collectively shape consumer perception rather than exerting isolated effects. The results therefore reinforce the importance of examining brand similarity at an aggregate or holistic level.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings align with brand signaling theory and consumer confusion theory, which suggest that excessive similarity can weaken brand differentiation and affect consumer perception (Tülin Erdem, 1998); (Mitchell & Papavassiliou, 1999). The results extend these perspectives by demonstrating that the combined perception of brand similarity, rather than individual cues, plays a more decisive role in shaping brand loyalty.

From a practical standpoint, the findings suggest that maintaining a distinctive overall brand identity is more critical than focusing solely on individual design elements. Firms that fail to differentiate their brand identity may struggle to sustain consumer loyalty in competitive FMCG markets.

4. Conclusion

This study examined the differential impact of brand free-riding dimensions on brand loyalty among consumers of soap and detergent products in selected cities of Southern Ethiopia. The findings show that although all dimensions are positively associated with brand loyalty, only brand identity resemblance has a statistically significant effect when considered jointly. This highlights the dominant role of holistic brand identity in shaping consumer loyalty.

The study contributes to branding literature by reinforcing the view of brand free-riding as a multidimensional and perception-driven phenomenon. The findings extend brand signaling theory and consumer confusion theory by demonstrating that the combined perception of brand similarity plays a more decisive role in shaping consumer behavior than individual brand cues.

The results further indicate that maintaining a clear and cohesive overall brand identity is central to sustaining consumer loyalty in competitive FMCG markets. A lack of distinctiveness in brand identity may increase vulnerability to imitation-based competition and weaken long-term brand preference.

4.1 Theoretical Implications

This study contributes to the branding and consumer behavior literature by advancing the conceptualization of brand free-riding as a multidimensional construct. While prior research has largely examined imitation as a unified phenomenon, the present findings demonstrate that its dimensions do not exert equal influence on brand loyalty. In particular, the dominant effect of

brand identity resemblance highlights the importance of holistic brand perception over isolated cues.

The results extend brand signaling theory and consumer confusion theory by showing that the effectiveness of brand signals depends not only on individual elements but also on the overall coherence and distinctiveness of brand identity. This suggests that future research should move beyond single-cue analysis and adopt integrated frameworks to examine imitation-based competition and consumer responses.

4.2 Managerial Implications and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study conducted in selected cities of Southern Ethiopia, the following recommendations are proposed for firms operating in competitive FMCG markets, particularly in similar developing market contexts.

First, firms should prioritize building and maintaining a strong and distinctive overall brand identity. The results show that brand identity resemblance has the most significant influence on brand loyalty, indicating that consumers rely more on holistic brand perception than on individual elements. Therefore, companies should focus on ensuring that all aspects of their brand collectively convey a clear and unique identity.

Second, managers should ensure consistency across all brand-related touchpoints, including packaging, visual presentation, labeling, and overall positioning. Rather than treating these elements independently, firms should integrate them strategically to reinforce a cohesive brand image that is easily distinguishable in the marketplace.

Third, firms should avoid excessive similarity with competing brands, even at the level of individual design elements. Although some similarities may not independently affect loyalty, their combined effect can create strong perceptual overlap, which may reduce brand distinctiveness and increase consumer confusion.

Finally, companies should actively monitor and manage imitation practices in the market. Given the strong influence of identity-level similarity, imitation can dilute brand value and weaken consumer loyalty. Firms are therefore advised to adopt proactive strategies that strengthen brand differentiation and protect their overall brand identity in highly competitive retail environments.

5 Limitations and Future Research

This study is subject to certain limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the study is geographically limited to selected cities in Southern Ethiopia, which may restrict the generalizability of the results to other regions or market contexts. Second, the focus on the soap and detergent category, as a segment of FMCG products, may limit the applicability of the findings to other product categories with different levels of consumer involvement and brand sensitivity.

Future research can extend this study by examining brand free-riding across different geographic settings and product categories to enhance generalizability. Comparative studies across industries or countries may provide deeper insights into how contextual factors influence the relationship between brand similarity and consumer behavior. Additionally, future studies may explore moderating variables, such as consumer involvement or brand familiarity, to better understand the conditions under which different dimensions of brand free-riding exert stronger or weaker effects on brand loyalty.

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